

The temporality of user experience; exploring past and future in two car case studies

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Abstract The importance of understanding the temporal aspects of user experience (UX) has been recognized by the research community as well as by industry. Two studies of cars were performed to further investigate the temporality of user experience. In total 27 drivers participated in the studies; one study was *retrospective* investigating past experiences of cars, and one was *prospective*, researching expectations on future autonomous cars. A mix of qualitative methods was employed, encouraging the participants' reflections through mediation by creative elements. Overlapping themes in the studies were found, and a tentative model was developed based on a temporal sequence in terms of *Aquaintancing*, *Using* and *Transforming*. By breaking down the temporality of user experience into sequences and defining the aspects of UX characterizing each sequence, it is suggested that designers and researchers can be helped in understanding and approaching experiences at these different stages.

Keywords *User experience, Automotive design, User study methodology, Temporality, Autonomous cars*

Introduction

Summarized under the term "User Experience" (UX), researchers as well as industry have over the last couple of decades struggled with understanding more about users' emotional responses to and experience of and with products. This is true also for the car industry. Examples of vehicle UX research include the experience of specific in-car systems such as infotainment touch interfaces (Pitts, Skrypchuk, Attridge, & Williams, 2014), haptic interfaces (Väänänen-Vainio-Mattila et al., 2014) and head-up displays (Soro et al, 2014). The studies mainly address momentary experiences of these systems, i.e. they capture users' direct responses to interacting with the systems and their user interfaces. However, user experience is something that develops and changes over time (see for example Bødker & Klokmoose, 2012; Karapanos et al, 2009; Kujala et al., 2011). Nevertheless, studies investigating vehicle *long-term* user experiences are, to the authors' knowledge, considerably more scarce with few exceptions including a study on adaptive cruise control systems (Eckoldt, Knobel, Hassenzahl, & Schumann, 2012), and a study on parking assistant systems (Trösterer, Wurhofer, Rödel, & Tscheligi, 2014). In addition to lacking a long-term perspective, prospective insights are missing even though they are essential for providing information at early stages of design processes. There is thus a need to further investigate the temporal dimensions of user experience, also for the automotive industry.

User experience and temporality

User experience frameworks

Today, a number of different approaches exists which addresses the issue of emotions and experience. With

an emphasis on affect and emotional response, a basic model of product emotions was put forward by Desmet (2002). According to the model an emotion is the result of an appraisal process where the characteristics of the product are appraised against the concerns of the individual. When the characteristics of a product match the concerns of a user, positive emotions are elicited. When there is a mismatch, on the other hand, negative emotions are elicited.

Norman (2004) chose to describe three levels of emotion design; 'visceral design' referring to a product's appearance and appeal to the user's senses, 'behavioural design' related to, for instance ease-of-use, and 'reflective design', i.e. how the product appeals to the user's self-image, personal satisfaction and meaning over time.

Developing on the concept of experience, Hekkert and Desmet (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) defined product experience as "the entire set of affects that is elicited by the interaction between a user and a product, including the degree to which all our senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meanings we attach to the product (experience of meaning) and the feelings and emotions that are elicited (emotional experience)" (Hekkert, 2006, p.160).

Focusing on interaction and use, Hassenzahl et al. (2008) described user experience as constituted along two product dimensions; pragmatic and hedonic qualities. Pragmatic qualities of a product concern the "do-goals" of a product, i.e. practical goals of interaction such as making phone calls or uploading documents on a web site. The other category of goals, the "be-goals" of a product, concerns the hedonic

qualities, i.e. how the design enables human needs beyond the instrumental, such as “being close to another person” or “being competent at work”. Be-goals thus move the concept of user experience beyond purely task-related goals for product use.

User experience and temporality

Even though time may be an implicit dimension in the frameworks described earlier, they do not *specifically* address temporality, i.e. how user experience is evolving over time, acknowledging the transitions between anticipated use, momentary use and use over extended periods of time. The relevance of temporality in UX studies has been shown by Bødker and Klokmoose (2012) who, based on an interview study with iPhone users, described users as transitioning between excited states, stable states and unsatisfactory states. Another example is Karapanos et al. (2009) who described iPhone users’ temporal user experience in terms of *orientation, incorporation and identification*. The orientation phase refers to users’ initial experiences where they are excited or frustrated when encountering new functionality. In the incorporation phase, the product becomes meaningful in the users’ daily life, where usability and usefulness are important factors. Finally, in the identification phase, the product is connected to the users’ self-identity. Additional temporal UX research has investigated how hedonic and pragmatic factors (cf. e.g. Hassenzahl et al. 2008) interplay with the user experience, indicating that pragmatic factors (e.g. usability) is predominant for user experience judgments at initial stages of use, whereas hedonic values (e.g. aesthetic, stimulation) became more dominant over time (Kujala et al., 2011).

Related to the question of UX temporality is methodology. Even though temporality is a key factor in users’ experiences of and with products, the primary source of knowledge for evaluating UX is assessments of affective responses to products (e.g. by tools such as SAM and PrEmo) and/or experiences of short-term use (for an overview, see Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). This issue has been addressed by developing retrospective methodologies, i.e. tracing back usage over time, such as the UX Curve method (Kujala, Roto, Väänänen-Vainio-Mattila, Karapanos, & Sinnelä, 2011), the iScale (Karapanos, Martens, & Hassenzahl, 2012) and employing “temporal anchors” (Huang & Stolterman, 2014). The common feature of the mentioned methodologies is that they intend to entice users to describe their ‘journey of use’ in retrospect.

Prospective insights

Another methodological issue from a temporal perspective is the lack of prospective insights from UX studies. Insights for understanding disruptive innovations, i.e. designs that create new values and by this may disrupt the market, can be difficult to elicit from retrospective and momentary methods. As design involves enabling novel experiences, it would be beneficial if research was able provide information also in early stages of design processes, and on products where there are no predecessors. In the automotive area, an example of this type of product is

autonomous cars. Most premium car brands are in the process of prototyping autonomous cars, but none are as yet available for the general public.

One aspect of the prospective is *expectations* on future experiences. Expectations have been found to shape the later outcomes of experiences (see for example Karapanos et al., 2009; Trösterer, Wurhofer, Rödel, & Tscheligi, 2014) and are a recognized part of experience temporality (see for example McCarthy & Wright, 2010). Expectations are based on earlier experiences as well as the user profile and anticipated emotions (Yogasara & Popovic, 2011). In addition to retrospective studies, expectations therefore pose an interesting study case for temporal user experiences, and in the study the subject of experience is thus approached from two perspectives; retrospective and prospective.

Aim and approach

With the overall aim to gain further knowledge of UX temporality, this paper describes two case studies of temporal in-vehicle user experiences, the first with the overall purpose of understanding *past* experiences, and the second addressing expectations on *future* user experiences. Questions posed are: How are the users’ stories of past and future use constituted? Do the stories differ depending upon the retrospective or the prospective timeline? Are there common themes to learn from in the two perspectives?

The first study was *retrospective*, i.e. looking back at cumulative UX, over prolonged use of in-car systems, in this case between 3 months and 3 years (a more detailed description of the study can be found in Pettersson & Karlsson 2015). The second study was *prospective*, i.e. researching the expectations of future user experiences of autonomous cars (a more detailed description of the study can be found in Pettersson 2016). Both studies contained creative elements to stimulate rich reflection as it has been suggested that information is accessible in layers (Karlsson, 1996; Visser et al., 2005) and in order to reach the lower, more inaccessible, levels, ‘*mediating tools*’, such as product representations, cultural probes, photos, drawings, etc., can be employed (Brandt & Grunnet, 2000; Karlsson, 1996; Sanders et al., 2010). The outcome of the two studies were analysed and compared in order to identify common experience aspects and if these aspects had a temporal dimension.

Study 1

Method

The first study employed three methods for retrospective data collection from altogether 16 Swedish drivers. The methods were Contextual Interviews (Beyer & Holtzblatt, 1997), the UX Curve Method (Kujala et al., 2011), and Reflexive Photography (Harrington & Lindy, 1998), aimed to stimulate in-depth reflection by the introduction of creative elements and the situated context in the car.

Prior to the interviews, the participants were asked to take photographs that depicted experiences of

Figure 1. Example of a participant's photo (Participant 4), connected to experiences of relatedness during phone calls in the car, as well as the ease of use of the call list.

significant importance for them. Figure 1 provides one of the participant's photos, as an example.

The photographs were brought to the interview session, where the first part of the study took place in the participant's home or office. Questions regarding experiences over time were posed, and in accordance with the UX curve methodology the participants were asked to draw their experiences over time on a positive/negative and longitudinal scale, as well as mark out memorable experiences. The next part of the interviews took place in the participants' cars, so that the participants could show/act out any experiences important to them in the car. All interviews were recorded, transcribed in full and the content was analysed applying a qualitative data analysis (as described by, for instance Denzin and Lincoln (1998)) together with the UX curves notes and the photographs.

Findings

The participants' user experiences clearly evolved over time as the cars were explored and incorporated into daily life. Three user groups emerged in terms of the overall user experience trends.

- A minor part of the participants (N=3) had a very informed expectations and the overall experience remained stable over time; "...Since I was quite aware of what I'd bought and they (the car brand) delivered what I expected, it (the UX Curve) is quite a straight line." (P4).
- For the largest group of participants (N=9) their experiences exceeded expectations, where positive behaviours and emotions evolved over time.
- The third group (N=4), was increasingly disappointed over time. In this case mainly usability issues lowered the experience ratings after initial high expectation for functionalities.

Expectations for the systems were formative for the initial experiences of use. Most changes were noted in the first half of the UX curves, as the users were exploring the cars, finding shortages as well as benefits through active use. An example of a curve with early experiences is presented in Figure 2. The thrill associated with discovery and stimulation was apparent, all participants enjoyed learning more about using their new cars over time. A typical comment was: "When you get used to it (an in-vehicle system), you look for the next thing" (P3).

Figure 2. Example of a User Experience Curve (P7), with several initial experiences.

Three principal aspects were found to be formative for the long-term user experience of in-vehicle systems:

- Influence of other products. All participants had in-vehicle systems that were connected to smart phones, and expectations were transferred from the phones to the car; "You can't update and if you don't like it (the in-car GPS) you have paid a lot of money and you're stuck with it." (P4). The users also continuously compared the car to other technology in their life, such as computers.
- Influence of new behaviours. Secondly, new behaviours emerged over prolonged use and these new behaviours altered the experience considerably over time. Examples of such established behaviours and routines were the use of hands-free phone, using apps for monitoring the car from home and working in the car; "It is a nice feeling with modern technology that you feel you are in the office but you are still transporting yourself. I think it is a good feeling and you feel that you are effective and solving many things at once. I did it yesterday" (P 6). These established habits were formative to the UX over time.
- Influence of social settings. Thirdly, many experience stories concerned social aspects of using in-vehicle systems and social routines such as calling family members on the way home became important routines in the users' lives. Technology in the car was also often found to serve as an enabler for joint experiences, for example enjoying podcasts or audio books together with family members in the car, or using the car to simplify everyday social life; "When the children get tired in the car, and you can have them borrow your phone and pick songs on Spotify (to play through the car's infotainment system), they like that because they have the feeling that they control something" (P14).

Method

In the second study, 11 Los Angeles drivers took part. The study made use of the "Setting The Stage for Future Automotive Experiences" method (Pettersson, 2014), developed to support user reflections on temporal experiential dimensions of expectations. The participants were asked to sit inside a "car" outlined on the floor in a room (Figure 3). They were first asked about their current daily commutes, anchoring any stories in the participants' personal perspectives. They

Figure 3. The Stage before, during and after study 2.

were then encouraged to imagine and enact a routine drive in an autonomous car, engaging both body and mind in reflections of expectations on different stages of usage; i.e. initial use and long-term routines. The placement in the “car” was intended to offer contextualization of the on-road, in-car context, allowing actions to be enacted as they would be performed in a real car. In addition, questions were posed concerning topics such as expected value, emotional responses and attraction, and how these would change over time. The participants were also asked to rearrange/remove seats and make drawings of any desired design changes.

The sessions were video- and audio-recorded and the audio-recording transcribed in full. As in Study 1, a qualitative content analysis was carried out (cf. Denzin & Lincoln, 1998) combined with Visser et al’s description of analysing generative methods for user studies (Visser et al., 2005).

Findings

The participants had high expectations for a smarter, efficient and relaxed life in the autonomous cars: “I would think like “wow I could be like, so amazingly efficient” (in an autonomous car). I could actually get in the car and get this done while the car is taking me to this destination, and then I could get that done too, and then do something else” (P1). Before actually daring to use the technology, they expected to make acquaintance with autonomous car through media, social connections, on the road and in showrooms. This phase was experienced as formative to later decision to trust the technology, and it was apparent that expectations were not formed in isolation but were heavily influenced by social and media influence; “(Trust) would depend on the vehicle manufacturer’s reputation and people I know in my social circle who may have experienced the technology.” (P24).

Attraction was expected to arise also from favourable aesthetics and novelty found in the interior of the car; “I think it would just be a new a canvas. I think you would have to lose all the regular car interior things, that we all know and use” (P20).

The participants all expected to eventually become engaged in using autonomous cars, although some more than others thought it would take time to gain trust. In expectations for active use, the participants related to previous use of other technology (e.g. semi-autonomous systems in current cars, smart phones and other domestic products), ease-of-use and stimulation. This included clear feedback and intuitive handling, but also the freedom of not having to control

functionality (unless specifically requested by the user); “Yeah, you can’t be involved (in traditional driving information) because you are completely immersed in another thought (when no longer engaged in driving the car). That’s not what that’s (the autonomous car) supposed to be. /.../ It has to be a new thing”. (P27)

In addition to the expectations on active use, autonomous cars were expected to make a tangible difference in the user’s life. This could for example be in form of introducing valuable new habits and routines during the daily commute, even having an effect on where to live; “Every place you go here is a distance so it would be a relief not to have to be “on” all the time. By the end of the day I’m often exhausted, a self-driving car would help me still do things. I don’t live in the heart of LA, so I have to drive a lot to do business and I can get sick of it. (...) I think it (an autonomous car) would change my evening routine, since I wouldn’t be as drained after a day of driving”. (P21). The meaning of the car was expected to transform, from today’s situation where control is extremely important, to being able to completely immersed in selected other activities, while being transported. The car was expected to create an augmented bridge between work and home life, bringing relief from unwanted emotions; “The car has no emotion and reacts exactly as it haves to, while you as a passenger avoided that set of emotions. /.../ Once I trust the car, many things that I think would make me anxious would no longer make me anxious. /.../ All the emotions and feelings that surround (LA traffic), that create the mood and transition from drive to home and make you upset with your kids, your wife, your dog, and so on. Now you have a smile. Less anger is transferred from the road to home (with an autonomous car).” (P19)

Cross-case analysis

The two studies investigated users’ past experiences of in-car systems (Study 1) and expected future experiences of and with an autonomous car (Study 2). Even so, overlapping themes were found, such as information of what made/would make the participants *attracted* to the car, how they experience/would experience *use* and how they had seen/expected to see their habits and relation to the car and its systems *transform* over time. Based on the narratives, these themes could be arranged in a temporal sequence. The sequence can be described as *Aquaintancing, Using and Transforming* (Figure 4.). Rejection took place when users had not been/was expected not to be attractive enough during *Aquaintancing*, or had/would lead to an unsatisfactory use situation, or unable to establish acquire habits and value of use over time. In accordance to this, the model highlights the process of user experience; transition from one stage to another is reached if the previous stage is satisfying.

In the narratives certain ascribed product features were emphasized in the different stages but also other things than the cars’ attributes influenced the experiences, such as social relations, expectations regarding other products, earlier interactions and

Figure 4. The tentative model of User Experience Temporality describing the “acquaintancing”, “using” and “transforming” sequences.

established routines connected to the car and daily habits. The factors are summarised in Table 1, and are not to be seen as set and stable, but give direction to the factors that foremost characterized each stage, as found in the two studies.

The first sequence, *Acquaintancing*, defines the stage where the user got/get to know the car before actual use. In both studies, a number of aspects were found to be influential, such as perceived novelty, aesthetics and functionality. A more complex interdependency was found to influence the ‘want’ for a new car than what Norman (2004) refers to as visceral aspects. In both studies it was also observed how acquaintancing was heavily influenced by social factors, such as friends talking about the technology in the car, interacting with salesmen or reading about it in social media. The acquaintancing phase set the expectations for later UX. In Study 1 the expectations influenced the outcomes of later experiences; in Study 2 this phase consisted of vividly imagining the future use where the expectations contained both “be-goals” and “do-goals” (cf. Hassenzahl et al., 2008). If the car was/will be found attractive enough to make the user trust and want the car, this “want” was/would be the lever that would enable actual use.

The second sequence, *Using* the car in an everyday life context contained elements such as ease-of-use (cf. Norman, 2004; Hassenzahl et al. 2008) and stimulation (cf. Hassenzahl et al., 2008) but also building trust in the car by interacting with it and its systems. An important aspect is that this sequence in itself contained temporal dimensions, i.e. stimulation and trust had/were expected to evolve over time, something which is overlooked in most user experience studies (Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). In Study 1 stimulation represented encountering new and sometimes unexpected features over time, such as updateable interfaces offering continuous stimulation. In Study 2 stimulation signified the initial confirmation of the novelty of the autonomous car, but also (over time) liberating the user to be entertained by

non-car related activities. In both studies, trust referred to predictable, transparent and reliable functionality but in Study 2 trust was further highlighted as a precondition for use, and was expected to grow over time. A use situation where these aspects were satisfactory was/would be the next lever into the next experience sequence.

The final sequence of *Transforming* describes how the car made/will make a long-term difference to the user, by new behaviours and assigned meaning of the car. This sequence encompasses the aspects of user experiences that are foremost established over prolonged use, i.e. identification, meaning and attachment, also present in the frameworks by Norman (2004) and Hassenzahl et al. (2008). However, this is also the sequence where the car transformed/was expected to transform everyday life. In Study 1, this was exemplified by the changes in work, leisure and social routines that the in-car technology offered. In Study 2, the autonomous car held far reaching expected possibilities of a less stressed and more efficient life in and with cars, even expected to influence where to live and work. These user experience aspects move well beyond sensory and interaction dimensions, i.e. from a micro-level on which the user experience the product through her senses, and cognitive and emotion responses to interaction, into a “macro-level” where the product plays a part in transforming the users’ activities and choices. This macro-level can be compared Forlizzi’s (2008) framework of Product Ecology where a web of social activities, life choices and practices are influenced by the artefact.

Discussion

The temporal model of user experience presented in this paper bears resemblance with the frameworks and models described earlier (cf. Norman, 2004 and Hassenzahl et al., 2008). However, the model emphasises the *temporal* aspects, including expectations as highlighted also by, for instance Olsson, Lagerstam, Kärkkäinen, and Väänänen-Vainio-

Table 1. User experience sequences.

	Acquaintancing	Active Use	Transformation
Aspects of UX	Aesthetics	Ease of use	Habits
	Functionality	Stimulation	Routines
	Novelty	Social influences	Attachment
	Social influences	Reability	Meaning(fullness)
	Trust building	Previous experiences of similar products	Self-identification
	...	Trust	...
		...	

Mattila (2011) and Yogasara and Popovic (2011). Furthermore, even though similarities exist in terms of addressing goal fulfilment, the last stage, *transforming*, is not incorporated in the models and frameworks mentioned. This last sequence in the model highlights the importance of new habits that are formed around products, and how the meaning (fullness) of the product may change over time, contributing to the overall user experience. What Hassenzahl et al. (2008) describe as “be-goals” of a product are thus not to be seen as set and stable. In the studies reported here they were rather found/were expected to transform. There is thus a dialectic relationship between product and user, extending beyond the direct experiences of product-user interactions. For example, the technology offered by a car may come to influence daily practices such as social routines or even more fundamental choices, such as where to live. It is possible that this expansion may not be relevant for less complex products but for the users involved in the studies, these experience aspects were essential and integrated parts of the overall user experience. The results highlight that as it is not possible to give an informed evaluation of a complex product, such as a car, from momentary instances of use. However, experience studies that do not address user experience over time are predominant (Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). In addition, based on the findings from Study 1, it does not appear feasible to filter out other products and people from research of user experience. Still, user experience studies commonly address only one user and one product. There is thus a need for a methodology that can provide further understanding of the longitudinal and “ecological” aspects of a product. Furthermore, the taxonomy of user experience could favourably be expanded; from a focus on direct interactions to also encompassing the “macro-perspective” of introducing new experiences that lead to evolved habits and routines that appear important in users’ lives. The model presented in this paper offers one suggestion of such an expansion of the user experience terminology.

The proposed model is based on two studies and further research is needed to confirm the relevance of the sequence as well as to develop on the aspects to consider in each phase. The first study describes how behaviours and experiences change over time, suggesting that there are limitations to what can be understood at one instance in time. This is evidently also true for prospective scenarios; there is not one, stable version of future experience. Nevertheless, as designers need to suggest versions of the future experiences, doing so with an informed user perspective is desirable. The tentative model can help researchers as well as designers to reflect on what aspects of user experience that can be accessible at what point in time of development. By breaking down the temporality of user experience into a sequence, designers and researchers can be enabled in understanding and approaching experiences at different stages. For example, with a novel product as an autonomous car, the interfaces must be designed to cater for the need of initial stimulation and novelty, as well as being allowed to fade into the background as

alternative activities and priorities emerge. The segmentation of the model could also aid the understanding of what aspects of user experiences one can address at what stage of evaluation. Furthermore, it highlights the need to design also for the development of habits and routines, as they become very important in the use and the experience of the product. As pointed out by for example Trösterer et al. (2014), habits evolving around *social behaviour* appear have a strong influence on user experiences. As time pass, the interface itself fades to the background and the activities it enables are the center of attention.

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